

PERCEPTION OF SCHOOL TEACHERS ON ENGLISH MEDIUM INSTRUCTION AT SECONDARY EDUCATION

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Abstract:

The medium of instruction is the language used by the teacher to teach. Teaching the language, or educational content, through the target language increases the amount of exposure the learner gets to it, and the opportunities they have to communicate in it, and therefore to develop their control of it. Present study is about the Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction at Secondary Education. Sample constitute 209 school teachers working in Virudhu Nagar district with due representation given to the 8 personal variables. Perception of school teachers on English medium instruction Scale constructed and standardized by Michael Leo, M. (2009) was employed to collect the data. Collected data were analysed by appropriate statistical treatment.

Key Words: Perception, Instruction & Communicate

Introduction:

A medium of instruction is a language used in teaching. It may or may not be the official language of the country or territory. Where the first language of students is different from the official language, it may be used as the medium of instruction for part or all of schooling. Bilingual or multilingual education may involve the use of more than one language of instruction. UNESCO considers that "providing education in a child's mother tongue is indeed a critical issue". It is unfortunate that in our country the question of the medium of instruction is a problem to be debated even after fifty years of independence. For in all civilized countries, the medium of instruction is the mother tongue. The advocates of English or Hindi make one mistake: they forget to main object of the medium of instruction. They fail to distinguish between a state language and a medium of instruction. The object is to also direct means for imparting education through mother tongue. It needs no argument to prove that the mother tongue helps the assimilation of knowledge in the impressionistic age, with the utmost ease. It is, therefore, the natural medium. Knowledge received through the mother tongue is always more concrete, abiding and intimate. That is why knowledge imparted through a foreign medium can never be satisfactory. Furthermore, it involves a great wastage of labour. Hence the researcher wants to know the perception of school teachers on English medium instruction at secondary education level. Hence the conduct of the current study.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To measure the level of Perception of school teachers on English medium instruction at secondary education.
- ✓ To find out, whether there is a significant difference among high school students in terms of select independent variables in their Perception on English medium instruction.

Methodology in Brief:

Design : Descriptive
 Method : Normative
 Technique : Survey

Sample: A sample of 209 high school teachers in Virudhu Nagar District served as the subjects of the study.

Tools Used:

- ✓ Personal Information Schedule
- ✓ Perception of school teachers on English medium instruction Scale constructed and standardized by Michael Leo, M. (2009).

Statistical Treatment: 't' test between the large independent samples.

Findings:

Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction and Age:

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of perception of school teachers on English medium instruction in terms of Age is presented in Table 1

Table 1: Statistical Measures and Results of Test of Significance for Difference Between the Means of Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction: Age Wise

Variable	Sub-Variables	N	Mean	SD	't' - Value	Significance at 0.05 Level
Age	Upto 40	104	25.451	3.332	2.528	Significant
	41 And Above	105	24.133	4.165		

The obtained 't' value 2.528 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in perception of school teachers on English medium instruction between the teachers, whose age is upto 40 and, 41 and above. It is further noted that the teachers whose age is upto 40 have favourable perception on English medium instruction at secondary education than the teachers whose age is 41 and above.

Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction and School Management:

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of perception of school teachers on English medium instruction in terms of School management are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Statistical Measures and Results of Test of Significance for Difference Between the Means of Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction: School Management Wise

Variable	Sub-Variables	N	Mean	SD	't' - Value	Significance at 0.05 Level
School Management	Govt	139	25.338	4.297	3.588	Significant
	Self-Financing	70	23.700	2.299		

The obtained 't' value 3.558 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in perception of school teachers on English medium instruction between the teachers who are working in government and self-financing schools. It is further noted that the teachers who are working in government schools have favourable perception on English medium instruction at secondary education than the teachers who are working in self-financing schools.

Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction and Specialization Subject:

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of perception of school teachers on English medium instruction in terms of Specialization Subject are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Statistical Measures and Results of Test of Significance for Difference Between the Means of Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction: Specialization Subject Wise

Variable	Sub - Variables	N	Mean	SD	't' - Value	Significance At 0.05 Level
Specialization Subject	Language	119	25.941	3.578	5.334	Significant
	Others	90	23.266	3.603		

The obtained 't' value 5.334 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in perception of school teachers on English medium instruction between the teachers whose specialization is Language and Other subject. It is further noted that the teachers whose specialization is Language have favourable perception on English medium instruction at secondary education than the teachers whose specialization is other subject.

Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction and Teaching Experience:

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of perception of school teachers on English medium instruction in terms of Teaching experience is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Statistical Measures and Results of Test of Significance for Difference Between the Means of Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction: Teaching Experience Wise

Variable	Sub-Variables	N	Mean	SD	't' - Value	Significance At 0.05 Level
Teaching Experience	Upto 10 Years	132	24.242	3.479	2.618	Significant
	11 and Above Years	77	25.727	4.207		

The obtained 't' value 2.618 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in perception of school teachers on English medium instruction between the teachers who have upto 10 years of experience and, 11 and above years of experience. It is further noted that who have 11 and above years of experience have favourable perception on English medium instruction at secondary education than the teachers who have upto 10 years of experience.

Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction and Books Reading Habit:

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of perception of school teachers on English medium instruction in terms of Books reading habit is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Statistical Measures and Results of Test of Significance for Difference Between the Means of Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction: Books Reading Habit Wise

Variable	Sub Variables	N	Mean	SD	't' - Value	Significance at 0.05 Level
Books	Regularly	56	23.750	2.406	3.049	Significant

Reading Habit	Rarely	153	25.169	4.165		
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The obtained 't' value 3.049 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in perception of school teachers on English medium instruction between the teachers who reads book regularly and rarely. It is further noted that the teachers who reads book rarely have favourable perception on English medium instruction at secondary education than the teachers who reads book regularly.

Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction and Marital Status:

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of perception of school teachers on English medium instruction in terms of marital status is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Statistical Measures and Results of Test of Significance for Difference Between the Means of Perception of School Teachers on English Medium Instruction: Marital Status Wise

Variable	Sub-Variables	N	Mean	SD	't' - Value	Significance at 0.05 Level
Marital Status	Married	175	24.240	3.840	7.264	Significant
	Unmarried	34	27.617	2.117		

The obtained 't' value 7.264 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in perception of school teachers on English medium instruction between the teachers who are married and unmarried. It is further noted that the teachers who are unmarried have favourable perception on English medium instruction at secondary education than the teachers who are married.

Conclusions:

Perception of school teachers on English medium instruction at secondary education in favour of the teachers

- ✓ Who are upto 40 years of age than those who are 41 and above
- ✓ Who are working in government schools than self-financing schools
- ✓ Whose specialization is language than other subject
- ✓ Who have 11 and above years of experience than those who have upto 10 years of experience
- ✓ Who reads rarely than those who reads regularly
- ✓ Who are unmarried than those who are married

Educational Implications:

This study reveals that the high school teachers who are upto 40 years of age, those who are working in government schools, who are handling language subject, who have 11 and above years of experience, who have reads book rarely and who are unmarried have favourable perception on English medium instruction at secondary education than their counterparts. Hence the counterparts should be facilitated through proper training for developing their Perception on English medium instruction at secondary education because reading writing and speaking in English is necessary component for job recruitment, getting admission in professional courses.

Suggestions for Further Research:

- The present study has enormous scope for the following further studies:
- ✓ The replica of the present study with the other type of schools.
 - ✓ The replica of the present study with the other variables
 - ✓ The replica of the present study with the college teachers.
 - ✓ The replica of the present study with the other type of research instruments.
 - ✓ The replica of the present study with the other districts.

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